

Automating ISCO Coding of Multilingual Survey Data Using an Agentic RAG Pipeline

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Abstract

Accurate occupational classification is essential for educational and sociological research, yet manual coding of free-text survey responses remains expensive, inconsistent, and difficult to scale. This challenge is magnified in multilingual settings where inputs may combine several languages, contain severe spelling errors, or reflect limited respondent knowledge. We present an agentic retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) pipeline for the automatic assignment of International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO) codes to free-text parental occupation descriptions collected through Luxembourg's *Épreuves standardisées* school monitoring program. The pipeline integrates two domain-specific knowledge stores – an enriched ISCO store and a Luxembourg-specific glossary – and delegates retrieval decisions to a large language model, allowing it to dynamically query the most relevant sources for each input. Applied to a dataset of 24,222 entries spanning up to nine languages, the pipeline produces results broadly consistent with Luxembourg's occupational distribution as measured by the SILC survey. On a sample of 500 entries independently coded by a human expert, the pipeline achieved 79.80% accuracy at the 4-digit ISCO level with a mean absolute deviation (MAD) in ISEI scores of 1.34 points, compared to 54.20% accuracy and a MAD of 4.12 points for the human coder. We further introduce two novel quality indicators – classification certainty and respondent seriousness – and establish empirically motivated thresholds for their use in downstream analyses. To our knowledge, this is the first study to apply agentic RAG to occupational classification in a multilingual minority-language setting, and the first to address noise introduced by children as proxy respondents in large-scale survey data.

Keywords: ISCO classification; occupational coding; retrieval-augmented generation; multilingual NLP; socioeconomic status; survey automation

1. INTRODUCTION

Occupation plays an important role in shaping many aspects of people's lives. It is directly related to their income, health, social mobility, and even political behavior (Ganzeboom and Treiman, 1996). In the education sector specifically, parental occupations are a key proxy for socioeconomic backgrounds and are routinely used to explain achievement gaps between students (OECD, 2023).

To make cross-national and longitudinal comparisons, it is necessary to have a standardized occupational classification system. This system must be well-adhered to, in a way that is as consistent as possible.

The International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO), developed by the International Labour Organization (ILO), is the most widely adopted occupational classification system internationally, serving as the basis for labor market statistics, cross-national research, and national classification schemes across member states (Hoffmann et al., 1995). Its hierarchical four-digit structure organises over 400 occupations into major, sub-major, minor, and unit groups. To illustrate this structure, consider the following example:

ISCO-08 Code Structure Example

The occupation **Economist** is encoded as **2632**, demonstrating how each digit level progressively refines the classification:

2000	Professionals (Major Group)
2600	Legal, social and cultural professionals (Sub-major Group)
2630	Social and religious professionals (Minor Group)
2632	Economists (Unit Group)

This hierarchical coding system ensures consistent occupational classification across diverse labor markets and statistical systems worldwide. However, it does not, in itself, carry a measure of socioeconomic status. This is addressed by the International Socio-Economic Index (ISEI), a separate index developed by Ganzeboom, De Graaf, and Treiman (1992) that assigns a continuous score to each ISCO code based on the education and income levels typically associated

with the corresponding occupation. Originally developed for ISCO-68 (Ganzeboom, De Graaf, and Treiman, 1992; ILO, 1969), the index has since been updated to align with ISCO-88 (Ganzeboom and Treiman, 1996; ILO, 1990) and ISCO-08 (Ganzeboom, 2010; ILO, 2012). ISEI scores range roughly from 10 to 90 and are widely used in educational and sociological research as a measure of socioeconomic background, and they are the ultimate quantity of interest in this project.

Since ISEI scores are used directly as a numerical predictor in regression models and group comparisons, even small classification errors can introduce systematic bias into downstream analyses – a concern that would apply regardless of whether the target variable is quantitative or qualitative, but is particularly consequential here given the direct mapping between ISCO codes and ISEI values. For instance, a university teacher is encoded with ISCO 2310 and has an ISEI score of 76, while a primary school teacher is encoded with ISCO 2341 and has an ISEI score of 61. While both occupations are closely related and belong to the same submajor group, their ISEI scores present a difference of 15, which is quite substantial on this small scale and has potential to introduce systematic bias. Across many surveys, occupations are still commonly classified into ISCO codes through manual coding (Bach et al., 2025). Unfortunately, manual coding is expensive, slow, difficult to scale, and may be inconsistent across coders, especially for vague inputs. Automation is therefore not merely convenient but necessary for modern large-scale research.

This is particularly critical in the context of Luxembourg, a multilingual country with three official languages (Luxembourgish, French and German) and a population of which over half are foreign nationals (STATEC, n.d.). The *Épreuves standardisées* (ÉpStan, “standardized tests”), a Luxembourgish school monitoring program in the form of written or online tests and questionnaires, provides a compelling case in point. Its aim is to record students' competences in key school areas, while considering the students' socioeconomic and sociocultural backgrounds (Épreuves Standardisées, 2024).

One of the topics covered in this questionnaire is parental occupations, which in secondary school are collected as free-text responses, resulting in inputs that may combine multiple languages in a single entry, contain severe spelling mistakes, are not serious, or reflect a child's

limited knowledge of their parent’s actual job. These characteristics render most traditional classification methods inadequate and call for a more robust, language-agnostic approach, which was confirmed empirically by the preliminary experiments described below.

Before the approach presented in this study, we tested several more traditional classification tools to process the inputs. A total of over 150,000 pre-classified records were available for the task, which is substantial enough for a classic train–test methodology.

The first baseline classifiers that were evaluated were linear regression and gradient-boosted decision trees, implemented with both sparse text vectorization (TF-IDF) and multilingual sentence embeddings (LaBSE). Despite hyperparameter tuning, their performance proved insufficient given the complexity of the data, barely exceeding an accuracy of 60% at the unit level (4-digit ISCO codes).

A third approach was k-nearest neighbors (k-NN), also tested with both TF-IDF and LaBSE settings. Once again, despite tuning and testing various distance metrics, the best results were close to those of the previously tested methods and were deemed unsatisfactory.

Several characteristics of the dataset likely explain these limitations. First, the official list of ISCO labels contains over 600 unique codes, which typically requires much larger training datasets for reliable multiclass classification. Second, the dataset is highly unbalanced: some occupations appear hundreds of times while others may occur only a handful of times, or not at all. Finally, the multilingual nature of the data presents an additional challenge. Even advanced preprocessing tools struggle with inputs that combine multiple languages within the same sentence and contain severe spelling errors. This is particularly true for Luxembourgish, a minority language that has only recently been standardized and whose spelling conventions and lexical resources are still evolving (Gabriel, 2024; Gouvernement du Grand-Duché de Luxembourg, 2018).

Taken together, these factors suggest that the limitations encountered are not merely a matter of model choice or hyperparameter tuning but rather reflect a mismatch between standard text-classification approaches and the specific characteristics of the data. This points toward an alternative approach – one capable of leveraging external knowledge sources and reasoning over ambiguous inputs, rather than relying solely on patterns learned from training data.

In response to these challenges, this study proposes an agentic retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) pipeline designed specifically for multilingual and noisy occupational descriptions. Unlike previous approaches, the system dynamically retrieves information from two domain-specific knowledge bases: an enriched ISCO repository and a Luxembourg-specific glossary, allowing the model to access contextual information beyond simple job titles or synonyms. The approach also introduces two quality indicators, classification certainty and respondent seriousness, which allow unreliable cases to be identified and filtered in downstream analyses. To our knowledge, this is the first study to apply agentic RAG to occupational classification in a multilingual minority-language setting.

2. RELATED WORK

The automation of occupational coding, that is, the assignment of standardized codes to free-text job descriptions, has been a recurring challenge in survey research for decades (Hoffmann et al., 1995; Ganzeboom and Treiman, 1996). As datasets grow larger and manual coding becomes increasingly impractical, the field has explored a wide range of approaches – from rule-based string matching to machine learning and, more recently, large language models.

Lagios et al. (Lagios et al., 2023) propose the most traditional of the recent multiclass classification methods, using a neural network with a direct weight-determination method (WASD). Applied to two publicly accessible ISCO datasets, their WASDMC model achieved 97.8% and 93.3% accuracy respectively, substantially outperforming competing classifiers. Importantly, their approach requires pristine input data

as it relies on exact string matching and is thus not applicable for multilingual and/or noisy data.

Schierholz and Schonlau (Schierholz and Schonlau, 2021) compared various machine learning algorithms for occupation coding across multiple German survey datasets, finding accuracies ranging from 35% to 69%, with no single method consistently outperforming others, highlighting the limitations of pre-LLM approaches.

Gnehm and Clematide (Gnehm and Clematide, 2025) tackle a slightly different task, but their dataset has a very important similarity to the one used in this project: multilingualism. The authors classify occupations mentioned in Swiss job postings which are composed of German, French, English and Italian listings. They use pre-fine-tuned models and LLM evaluations to filter and reweight training data, reducing noise and improving multilingual performance, increasing the proportion of correct first predictions from 37.2% to 58.3% and achieving up to 80% correct classifications on previously unseen data.

Langezaal et al. (Langezaal, Broek, Peters, et al., 2023) developed a support system called OPERAS, a pre-LLM, machine learning methodology for occupational coding. The main objective was to underline the importance of automation of such tasks – OPERAS achieved inter-coder reliability (Cohen’s Kappa) of 0.66–0.84 at the most detailed coding level, significantly outperforming expert coders (0.59–0.76) while reducing coder workload by an estimated 20–56%.

The closest methodological predecessor to this study is the approach presented by Bach et al. (Bach et al., 2025). The authors address multilingual job description entries using retrieval-augmented generation (RAG, (Lewis et al., 2020)), allowing a large language model to play a central role in the classification process. Their best-performing model (o3) achieved 73% Top-1 accuracy on full 4-digit ISCO codes, with GPT-4.1 (OpenAI, 2025) reaching 61%. While methodologically related, the approach proposed in this study differs in several key aspects. First, rather than relying on a single knowledge base composed mainly of occupational titles, synonyms, and expert annotations, the pipeline integrates multiple domain-specific knowledge stores, including an enriched ISCO repository and a Luxembourg-specific glossary. Second, retrieval decisions are delegated to the language model itself, allowing it to dynamically query the most relevant source depending on the input. Third, the system is designed to handle extremely noisy and multilingual inputs, including mixtures of several languages and substantial spelling errors typical of child-reported survey responses. Finally, the present study introduces two additional quality indicators: classification certainty and respondent seriousness, which provide a way to assess classification reliability and filter problematic responses in downstream analyses.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data

As introduced above, the data used in this project was obtained from secondary school online questionnaires from the yearly Épreuves Standardisées. Each student is asked about their parents’ occupations in the form of a job title and a job description, yielding a total of 4 inputs per student. In an approach modelled on the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (OECD, 2023), student responses are ultimately used to derive the International Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status ISEI-08 (International Labour Office, 2012).

Based on our analysis of the dataset, the most persistent challenge is the multilingual nature of the inputs: a single entry may draw on two or three languages simultaneously. Compounding this are spelling errors, children’s incomplete knowledge of their parents’ occupations, and a non-negligible share of non-serious responses – all of which make reliable automated classification substantially harder.

As previously mentioned, the raw data presents 4 inputs per student: mother’s job title, mother’s job description, father’s job title, and father’s job description. They are reformatted into 2 rows per student with 2 columns each: one row for mother’s job and description, as

well as one row for father's job and description.

Table 1 briefly summarizes the formatted data as given to the LLM:

Table 1. Dataset Overview

Metric	Value
Total number of rows	24,222
Number of languages detected by tiktoken ¹	9 (de, fr, en, lb, es, pt, it, nl, af) ²
Total number of tokens in input data	213,265
Average number of tokens per row	8.80
Minimum number of tokens per row	0
Maximum number of tokens per row	81

¹ encoding for gpt-5-mini

² German, French, English, Luxembourgish, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian, Dutch, Afrikaans

This summary makes two points very clear: no matter the classification method chosen, it must be robust with respect to multiple languages, and it must be computationally efficient given the large amount of data to process.

3.2. Knowledge Base

The next step consists of constructing two knowledge stores, the ISCO store and the glossary store.

The ISCO store is made up of two parts: first, the official ISCO structure retrieved from (International Labour Office, 2012) and second, a custom-made list of Luxembourg-specific remarks related to particular codes, containing for instance guidance such as: code 9110 (*Cleaners and helpers, not elsewhere classified*) should be used for non-specific cleaning personnel – entries such as “Botzfra”, “Putzfrau”, or “femme de ménage” – unless it is explicitly stated which type of establishment this person cleans.

For each unique code, the official ISCO structure contains an official job title, definition, description of tasks and duties, examples of occupations and examples of tangent occupations that should be classified under a different code. All of these were considered essential, as in many cases the difference between two occupations may be extremely subtle and not deducible from solely a title and a brief description.

The ISCO data is loaded and merged with French and German title translations, the ISEI scores and the Luxembourg-specific occupation data. ISCO codes shorter than 4 digits must be zero-padded (by default, they are interpreted as integers and codes such as 0120 become 120). Each occupation entry is converted into a structured text chunk and embedded using a pre-trained sentence embedding model. The resulting vectors are stored in a local vector database, which enables semantic similarity search – that is, given a query, the system retrieves the entries whose meaning is closest to the input, rather than relying on exact keyword matching. Both stores are queried through the same interface, returning the top 7 most relevant candidates along with their relevance scores. Full implementation details are available upon request.

The glossary store is also made of two components: a glossary file and a list of Luxembourg secondary schools with their official abbreviations, which are combined into a second ChromaDB collection. The glossary could be compared to a Luxembourg-specific dictionary, where various entries are combined: from institution names to colloquial Luxembourgish words. The main goal was to cover any type of entry repetitive enough to significantly affect results, but so distinct that an LLM could not accurately handle it by itself.

The knowledge base is loaded only once at the beginning and shared across all threads.

3.3. Agentic classification

The model chosen for this task was `gpt-5-mini` and accessed via the OpenAI Chat Completions API. Initially, previous versions of the model were explored; however, `gpt-3` struggled with linguistic nuances and vague inputs, while `gpt-4` was notably more expensive than the “mini” variant of its successor.

For each input, a conversation is initialized with a system prompt and the job description as user message. The LLM is given access to the tools allowing it to query the ISCO and glossary stores, in a way that it autonomously decides whether to call any of the tools, and if so which one and with what search query. The results are appended to the message history, and the model is called again. This loop is set to repeat for a total of 5 iterations (in practice, most often 1-3 iterations).

3.4. Output Parsing

Once the loop is finished, the output produces a final text response; the output is parsed. If the code is valid, it is matched against the ISCO reference table to retrieve the English title and ISEI value. Un-classifiable descriptions are encoded with the non-existent ISCO code 9999. The expected format has been structured as follows:

Table 2. Dataset Column Descriptions

Column	Description
job_description	Concatenated job title and description
isco	ISCO code chosen by LLM
pct_certain	Measure of how certain the LLM is of its classification
pct_serious	Measure of how seriously the task was taken by the questionnaire respondent
isco_title	Official ISCO job title
isei	Official ISEI score
explanation	LLM's reasoning
elapsed_seconds	Time elapsed to process the row
any_tools_used	Information if any tools were used, Boolean
cost	Total row processing cost in dollars
model	LLM which was used to process the row
total_input	Total of input tokens
total_output	Total of output tokens

3.5. Illustrative Examples

The following fictional, but realistic examples illustrate how the pipeline handles the kinds of noisy and ambiguous inputs typical of the dataset. Each was constructed to reflect a specific challenge: an implicit occupational description, a creatively phrased response, and a text with significant spelling errors.

The first example is a relatively clear English description that does not name the occupation explicitly, yet provides enough contextual information for the pipeline to arrive at the correct code:

```

Input: i dont know how its called but he changes the seats in
      ↪ airplanes when they have holes or are broken
Output: ISCO Code: 7534
Certainty: 100% | Seriousness: 95%
Elapsed: 12.79 seconds
Tokens: 4871 in / 568 out | Cost: $0.0012319500

Explanation:
The description ("changes the seats in airplanes when they have
      ↪ holes or are broken") matches ISCO 7534 Upholsterers and
      ↪ Related Workers (vehicle/aircraft seat upholstery and
      ↪ repair). Not aircraft engine/airframe mechanics (7232) or
      ↪ assemblers (8211). High coding certainty because the
      ↪ task specifically concerns repairing/replacing upholstery
      ↪ of aircraft seats; student response appears genuine.

```

Code 1. Example 1

The second example is a German description in which the student clearly engaged with the task but lacked the precise occupational

term. The pipeline correctly inferred the intended occupation from the descriptive phrasing:

```

Input: so wie sherlock holmes er findet wahrheit
Output: ISCO Code: 3411
Certainty: 90% | Seriousness: 80%
Elapsed: 14.31 seconds
Tokens: 3918 in / 928 out | Cost: $0.0010027000

Explanation:
The student likens the parent to "Sherlock Holmes" - explicitly
↳ implying a detective/private investigator who "finds the
↳ truth." ISCO glossary shows "private detective" is
↳ classified under 3411 (Legal and related associate
↳ professionals). I considered police detective (3355) but
↳ the Sherlock Holmes reference strongly indicates a
↳ private investigator, so I assigned 3411 with high
↳ certainty. Seriousness rated as fairly high (short but
↳ coherent description, likely earnest).

```

Code 2. Example 2

The third example is a French description containing substantial spelling errors. Despite this, the pipeline identified the correct ISCO code:

```

Input: elekrisien il fais l'elekrisite
Output: ISCO Code: 7411
Certainty: 95% | Seriousness: 90%
Elapsed: 13.65 seconds
Tokens: 4680 in / 791 out | Cost: $0.0011897750

Explanation:
The phrase (misspelled French) reads "electricien, il fait l'
↳ electricite" - clearly an electrician doing electrical
↳ installation/repair. This matches ISCO 7411 (building and
↳ related electricians). Not an engineer or a household/
↳ domestic role, and the wording is a straightforward,
↳ serious description.

```

Code 3. Example 3

3.6. Parallelization

All job descriptions were processed in parallel using Python's `ThreadPoolExecutor` with 50 workers. The entire process lasted a total of 127.29 minutes. The average time per job was 0.32 seconds, and the throughput amounted to 190.28 jobs per minute.

Fig. 1 provides a visual overview of the full classification pipeline, from data ingestion to CSV output.

4. EVALUATION

The classification results are evaluated through two complementary approaches: a distributional comparison against external survey data covering the full set of 24,222 entries, and a direct accuracy assessment on a 500-entry subset independently coded by human experts. These are presented in turn below.

Out of 24,222 entries, 6,854 were deemed uncodable (9999) by the LLM, out of which 2,964 (43.2%) were empty. Among the remaining 3,890 non-empty uncodable entries, a manual inspection confirmed that the vast majority contained inputs that would be considered uncodable even by a human expert: entries consisting solely of a company name, stay-at-home parent indicators, or descriptions too abbreviated or ambiguous to permit reliable classification. This is consistent with the prompt instruction to return 9999 when no ISCO category can be matched with sufficient confidence, erring on the side of caution rather than forcing a classification.

Two additional output fields were used to assess classification quality: `pct_certain`, reflecting the model's confidence in its ISCO assignment, and `pct_serious`, reflecting its assessment of whether the student genuinely attempted to describe their parent's occupation.

Following an analysis of the output distribution, thresholds were set at 75% for `pct_certain` and 80% for `pct_serious`. Below the certainty threshold, classification accuracy was found to drop significantly. Below the seriousness threshold, outputs were frequently nonsensical, including responses suggesting a parent's occupation was a fictional creature. Entries falling below either threshold should therefore be treated with caution in downstream analyses.

Among the encoded entries, there were 289 major codes (1.66% of coded entries), 997 submajor codes (5.74%), 3,341 minor codes (19.24%) and 12,741 unit codes (73.36%). Entries assigned a code at less than the full 4-digit precision reflect cases where the LLM determined that a broader category could be assigned with higher certainty than any specific unit group code – a deliberate design choice in the system prompt, which explicitly instructs the model to prioritize certainty over specificity.

4.1. Distributional Comparison with SILC

The distribution of classified ISCO major groups is compared to external occupational distribution data provided by the National Institute of statistics and economic studies (STATEC) through the Survey on Income and Living Conditions (SILC), which collects socio-economic data on Luxembourg households, including income, housing, employment, health and well-being, with the aim of informing policies to combat poverty, inequality and social exclusion. The underlying assumption is that, if the classification is accurate, the distribution of parental occupations in the *ÉpStan* should broadly reflect the occupational distribution of the Luxembourg working population. To strengthen this comparison, STATEC provided two versions of the SILC data: one covering the general working population, and one restricted to households with dependent children – the latter being more directly comparable to the population of parents whose occupations are described in the questionnaire. It should be noted that the SILC data includes households with children of all ages, including very young children, while our data *ÉpStan* covers parents of grade 7 and 9 secondary school students specifically. Despite this slight discrepancy, we consider the populations sufficiently representative of Luxembourg's active working population to serve as a meaningful benchmark.

Fig. 2 represents the comparison of the agentic RAG classification (2025) versus the SILC results (2025)¹.

For most major groups, the results provided by the agentic RAG were very close to the ones of the SILC survey, half of the time within a 1% difference. The three major groups where the difference between both was more considerable were 2, 5 and 9. While many scenarios may be possible, the following hypotheses come to mind:

The major group 2 represents professionals, including many occupations that may not be obvious for children to describe, such as mining engineer, organization analyst, policy administrator professional or curator. After an analysis of the inputs that were deemed uncodable, it has been found that a considerable number of cases contain key words such as "office" or "computer", indicating that there is a strong chance that multiple of these entries could belong to the major group 2, which could partially explain the gap between the agentic RAG method and the results of the SILC survey.

Concurrently, the major group 5 of service and sales workers, which is around half the size of the major group 2, is mostly comprised of titles that may be considered relatively straightforward. For instance, it includes occupations such as "cook", "hairdresser", "cashier" or "firefighter". It can reasonably be assumed that occupations in major group 5 are, on average, easier for children to understand, remember, and describe than occupations in major group 2.

A similar observation can be made on major group 9 which represents elementary occupations. This includes occupations such as "domestic cleaner", "farmer" or "garbage collector".

¹ It should be noted that in the 2025 SILC there were no participants from the major group 0

Figure 1. Agentic RAG pipeline for ISCO classification

Figure 2. Distribution of ISCO codes by first digit (Agentic RAG vs. SILC Survey)

Overall, the distributional comparison with the SILC survey suggests that the agentic RAG pipeline produces results that are broadly consistent with the known occupational structure of Luxembourg’s working population. The observed discrepancies in major groups 2, 5 and 9 are plausibly explained by the nature of the input data rather than systematic classification errors – specifically, the apparent difficulty children face in accurately describing cognitively or administratively complex occupations. This interpretation is further supported by the analysis of uncodable entries, which reveals a concentration of vague, office- or computer-related descriptions that are likely misclassified or excluded rather than genuinely absent from the Luxembourg labor market. Taken together, these results suggest that the pipeline is a reliable and scalable tool for large-scale occupational classification in multilingual, noisy survey settings, with residual limitations that are largely attributable to data quality rather than methodological shortcomings.

4.2. Comparison with Human Coders

This evaluation involves two distinct human coders whose roles differ fundamentally. The first coder, referred to here as the *production coder*, was a freelance expert hired to classify parental occupations at scale, working under realistic large-scale coding conditions with limited time for deliberation per entry. The second coder, referred to as the *gold standard coder*, consisted of the research team, for whom exactness took absolute priority: ambiguous cases were discussed at length, cross-referenced against the official ISCO documentation, and resolved collaboratively. The gold standard labels produced by the second coder serve as the reference against which both the pipeline and the production coder are evaluated. This setup reflects real-world conditions, where the relevant question is not whether an automated system can outperform a careful expert with unlimited deliberation time, but whether it can outperform the kind of coding that actually takes place in practice.

The pipeline’s output was compared to the labels given by the production coder, yielding the results summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Pipeline vs. human coder – 4-digit ISCO accuracy on 500-entry sample

Outcome	Count (%)
Both correct	230 (46.00%)
Pipeline correct, human wrong	169 (33.80%)
Human correct, pipeline wrong	41 (8.20%)
Both wrong	60 (12.00%)
Pipeline accuracy	79.80%
Human accuracy	54.20%

The pipeline substantially outperforms the human coder at the 4-digit level, achieving 79.80% accuracy against 54.20%. To assess whether this advantage holds at coarser levels of the ISCO hierarchy, accuracy was also computed at the major (1-digit), sub-major (2-digit), and minor (3-digit) group levels. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Accuracy by ISCO hierarchical level – pipeline vs. human coder

Level	Pipeline	Human
Major (1-digit)	96.14%	79.23%
Sub-major (2-digit)	93.39%	69.53%
Minor (3-digit)	91.80%	60.50%
Unit (4-digit)	79.80%	54.20%

The pipeline’s advantage grows as the classification becomes more granular – at the major group level the gap is 17 percentage points, widening to nearly 31 points at the 4-digit unit level. Notably, in cases where the two coders disagreed, the pipeline was correct and the human wrong in 33.56% of minor-level comparisons, while the reverse occurred in only 1.84% of cases, underscoring the pipeline’s consistency across the full hierarchy.

Beyond raw accuracy, the mean absolute deviation (MAD) in ISEI scores was computed to assess the socioeconomic impact of classification errors. For the pipeline, the overall MAD across all entries was 1.34 ISEI points; for the human coder it was 4.12 points. Restricting to incorrect classifications only, the pipeline’s MAD rises to 11.57 points while the human coder’s reaches 7.79 points – suggesting that when the pipeline does make an error, it tends to be a more confident one, whereas human errors are more evenly distributed. Crucially, the

pipeline's low overall MAD confirms that even its mistakes tend to be socioeconomically proximate to the correct code, limiting their downstream impact on ISEI-based analyses.

In addition to these performance metrics, the pipeline also demonstrates a clear advantage in terms of efficiency. Processing the full dataset of 24,222 entries required approximately 2 hours of automated computation, whereas the human expert coding of the same dataset was carried out over an estimated 300 hours of freelance work, requiring several weeks of sustained effort. This substantial difference in throughput, when considered alongside the pipeline's higher accuracy and consistency, highlights the practical value of automated classification for large-scale survey data.

5. DISCUSSION

The work presented in this article is, to our knowledge, the first application of agentic RAG to occupational classification in a multilingual minority-language setting. Unlike Bach et al. (2025), whose pipeline relies on a generic knowledge base of occupational titles and synonyms and follows a fixed retrieval structure, the approach presented here integrates domain-specific knowledge stores – including a Luxembourg-specific glossary and custom ISCO extensions – and delegates retrieval decisions to the LLM itself. This agentic design proved particularly valuable in handling the linguistic and contextual complexity of the data, allowing the model to dynamically query the most relevant sources rather than being constrained to a predetermined retrieval step. The pipeline achieves 79.80% top-1 accuracy at the 4-digit ISCO level, which is in line with Bach et al.'s best result of 73% (Bach et al., 2025). The difference, however, is a notable margin given that the present dataset is substantially noisier, multilingual, and collected from child respondents rather than adult survey participants. It also compares favourably with Gnehm and Clematide (2025), whose LLM-assisted approach reached 58.3% top-1 accuracy on silver-standard data and 80% precision on held-out data, though direct comparison is limited by differences in task design, classification granularity, and evaluation methodology.

Nevertheless, as with any automated tool, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, while the human coder comparison provides a direct accuracy estimate, the sample of 500 entries represents a small fraction of the full dataset, and the expert labels themselves carry some degree of subjectivity, particularly for ambiguous inputs. The SILC comparison, meanwhile, serves as a distributional plausibility check rather than a true accuracy measure – a limitation that is inherent to the data collection context rather than to the method itself. Second, codes above unit level (major, sub-major and minor) cannot always be attributed to a single cause: in some cases, they reflect genuine input vagueness, while in others they may reflect real ambiguity in the ISCO taxonomy itself, where sometimes even the correct major group for a job description is unclear. For example, ISCO 2221 “Nursing professionals” includes higher-responsibility tasks such as planning and evaluating nursing care, coordinating with other health professionals, supervising staff, and conducting nursing research, whereas ISCO 3221 “Nursing associate professionals” focuses on providing nursing and personal care, administering medication under established care plans, and assisting with monitoring and basic care. Although 2221 appears hierarchically more demanding in terms of responsibility and belongs to a higher major group, a student's description such as “My mother is a nurse at the hospital” may fit both unit groups equally well, illustrating that ambiguity can arise not only from vague inputs but also from overlapping task descriptions within the classification system itself. Finally, the glossary and Luxembourg-specific knowledge base required substantial manual curation effort, which limits the out-of-the-box transferability of the pipeline to other national contexts – though this effort would be considerably reduced for countries with more standardized linguistic environments.

Looking more closely at the data, the use of children as proxy respondents introduces a unique and underexplored source of noise in

occupational data collection that deserves attention beyond this study. Children's limited understanding of their parents' roles, combined with varying levels of engagement with the questionnaire, produces a type of input noise that differs fundamentally from the adult survey noise typically addressed in the occupational coding literature. In this regard, the seriousness and certainty thresholds introduced in this study represent a novel quality filtering mechanism that may prove useful in other survey contexts where respondent engagement cannot be guaranteed. Similarly, the analysis of uncodable entries may be thought of as a diagnostic tool in its own right – one that reveals not only the limits of the classification method but also broader patterns in how occupational data is collected and reported.

More broadly, the cost and time efficiency of the pipeline – processing over 24,000 entries in approximately two hours at a very modest API cost – makes a strong case for replacing manual coding in large-scale survey contexts. With appropriate knowledge base adaptation, this approach has considerable potential to be extended to other countries and institutional settings. This carries implications for large-scale educational surveys such as PISA, which rely heavily on parental occupational data to construct socioeconomic indicators. As LLM capabilities continue to improve and costs continue to fall, agentic RAG-based pipelines of this kind may soon represent the standard approach to occupational classification in survey research – combining the interpretive flexibility of human coders with the speed and scalability that modern data collection demands.

6. CONCLUSION

This study presented an agentic retrieval-augmented generation pipeline for the automatic classification of parental occupations into ISCO codes, developed in response to the unique challenges posed by the *Épreuves standardisées* dataset. The combination of extreme multilingualism, a minority language with still-evolving spelling norms, severe input noise, and children as proxy respondents created a classification problem that traditional supervised methods consistently failed to solve. By integrating domain-specific knowledge stores with LLM-based agentic reasoning, the pipeline achieved results broadly consistent with Luxembourg's known occupational distribution. On a 500-entry sample independently coded by a human expert, it reached 79.80% accuracy at the 4-digit ISCO level – substantially outperforming the human coder at 54.20% – with an overall MAD in ISEI scores of just 1.34 points, confirming that even classification errors tend to be socioeconomically proximate to the correct code. These results, combined with substantial gains in speed, scalability, and cost over manual coding, make a strong case for its adoption in large-scale survey workflows.

The quality filtering mechanisms introduced, based on model-reported certainty and seriousness thresholds, further enhance the reliability of the output for downstream statistical analyses. While limitations remain, particularly around ground truth validation and transferability to other national contexts, this work demonstrates that agentic RAG represents a promising and practical solution for occupational classification in complex, multilingual survey settings.

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■ DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTERESTS

The author declares that she has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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